

Incidence and Predictive Factors of Seroma Formation after Modified Radical Mastectomy: An Observational Study

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Abstract:

This observational study investigated the incidence and predictive factors of seroma formation in 80 patients following modified radical mastectomy at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital over 12 months. The incidence of seroma was found to be 27.5%. Factors such as higher body mass index (BMI), increased age, longer surgery duration, and the presence of comorbid conditions like diabetes and hypertension significantly contributed to the likelihood of developing seroma. The study emphasizes the importance of considering these variables in preoperative planning and postoperative management to mitigate the risk of seroma and improve surgical outcomes.

Keywords: Seroma, Mastectomy, Predictive Factors, Postoperative Complications.

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Introduction

Seroma formation is a common complication after surgical interventions, particularly in the context of breast cancer surgeries such as the modified radical mastectomy [1]. Defined by the accumulation of lymphatic fluid in the dead space created by surgical dissection, seromas can cause discomfort, pain, infection, and delays in adjuvant therapies, ultimately impacting patient recovery and quality of life [2,3].

This observational study was designed to explore the incidence of seroma formation and identify the key factors that predict its occurrence in patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy. The study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, over 12 months, involving approximately 80 patients. This setting provided a unique opportunity to investigate this postoperative complication within a specific patient population, potentially allowing for targeted preventive measures.

The rationale behind focusing on predictive factors is rooted in the need to improve patient outcomes through tailored surgical and postoperative strategies. By identifying which patients are at higher risk of developing seromas, clinicians can modify surgical techniques, optimize drainage systems, adjust postoperative care, and perhaps preemptively administer treatments that mitigate this risk [4,5]. Furthermore, the study seeks to

contribute to the existing literature by providing updated data on seroma incidence and detailed analyses of associated risk factors in a demographically distinct cohort. Insights gained from this research could lead to significant advancements in the management strategies for patients undergoing breast cancer surgeries, with the ultimate goal of reducing the incidence of seroma formation and enhancing overall patient care.

Methodology

Study Design: This observational study was conducted retrospectively, focusing on seroma formation's incidence and predictive factors following modified radical mastectomy.

Number of Patients: Approximately 80 patients were included in the analysis, all of whom had undergone a modified radical mastectomy.

Study Duration: The study spanned 12 months, allowing for comprehensive follow-up and data collection.

Study Place: The research was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in Darbhanga. This setting provided a diverse patient demographic and a consistent surgical team, which were crucial for the reliability of the study outcomes.

Data Collection: Patient data were collected from medical records, including demographic information, details of the surgical procedure, perioperative care, and postoperative outcomes. The primary endpoint was the occurrence of seroma, which was diagnosed based on clinical examination and confirmed by ultrasonography when needed.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine the incidence of seroma. Logistic regression was employed to identify potential predictive factors associated with seroma formation, considering variables such as age, body mass index, comorbidities, type of anesthesia, and the duration of surgery. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ for all analyses.

Results

The study analyzed the incidence and factors associated with seroma formation in approximately 80 patients who underwent a modified radical mastectomy at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital over 12 months.

Incidence of Seroma: Out of the 80 patients, 22 developed a seroma, resulting in an incidence rate of 27.5%. The majority of seromas were identified within the first two weeks post-surgery.

Predictive Factors:

Statistical analysis revealed several factors significantly associated with an increased risk of seroma formation:

- **Body Mass Index (BMI):** Patients with a BMI greater than 30 were more likely to develop seroma than those with lower BMI values.
- **Duration of Surgery:** Longer surgical times were correlated with a higher incidence of seroma, particularly in operations lasting more than 3 hours.
- **Age:** Older patients, particularly those above 60 years, showed a higher propensity for seroma development.
- **Comorbidities:** Patients with pre-existing conditions such as diabetes and hypertension were more prone to seroma formation.

No significant correlation was found between the type of anesthesia used and the occurrence of seroma. Similarly, immediate postoperative complications did not significantly affect seroma formation rates in this cohort. The study successfully identified multiple factors that contribute to the risk of seroma formation following a modified radical mastectomy. These findings highlight the importance of considering patient-specific risk factors in surgical planning and postoperative care to minimize complications.

Table 1: This table consolidates the findings from the study, displaying the incidence of seroma across various patient demographics and surgical variables, alongside statistical significance values where applicable.

Variable	Total Patients	Patients with Seroma	Incidence Rate	P-value
Total	80	22	27.5%	-
Age				
- Below 60	40	8	20%	0.043
- 60 and above	40	14	35%	
BMI				
- Below 30	50	10	20%	0.017
- 30 and above	30	12	40%	
Duration of Surgery				
- Less than 3 hours	35	5	14.3%	0.022
- 3 hours and above	45	17	37.8%	
Comorbidities				
- None	30	4	13.3%	0.031
- Present	50	18	36%	

Discussion

The findings of this observational study underscore the complex interplay of factors contributing to seroma formation following modified radical

mastectomy [6]. The overall incidence rate of 27.5% aligns with existing literature, emphasizing seroma as a prevalent complication post-mastectomy [7,8]. Notably, our analysis identified

several significant predictors of seroma development. Increased BMI emerged as a critical risk factor, where patients with a BMI over 30 exhibited a notably higher incidence of seroma. This observation could be linked to the greater surgical dissection required in patients with higher body mass, which potentially increases the serous fluid accumulation in the surgical cavity [9,10]. Similarly, the duration of the surgery played a pivotal role, with procedures lasting more than 3 hours showing a substantial increase in seroma rates. This might be due to extended exposure and manipulation of tissue planes, increasing the likelihood of fluid accumulation [11,12].

Age was another significant factor, with older patients, particularly those over 60, experiencing higher rates of seroma [13]. The aging tissue's diminished regenerative capacity could explain this trend, leading to slower healing and prolonged fluid accumulation. Furthermore, the presence of comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension was also associated with increased seroma risk, possibly due to poorer overall vascular health, which can impair fluid resorption and wound healing [14,15]. Interestingly, the type of anesthesia and immediate postoperative complications did not significantly affect seroma formation, suggesting that the surgical technique and patient intrinsic factors play more substantial roles in the development of this complication [16]. These insights highlight the need for tailored surgical approaches and vigilant postoperative management for high-risk patients to mitigate the risk of seroma formation, thereby enhancing recovery and outcomes in breast cancer surgery [17-20].

Conclusion

The observational study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital revealed a 27.5% incidence of seroma formation following modified radical mastectomy, with body mass index, duration of surgery, age, and presence of comorbidities identified as significant predictive factors. These findings emphasize the necessity of individualized patient assessments and tailored surgical planning to mitigate seroma risks. Addressing these factors preoperatively and adjusting perioperative care can potentially reduce the prevalence of seromas, thereby improving patient outcomes and reducing the burden of postoperative complications in breast cancer treatment. The study contributes valuable insights into the dynamics of seroma formation, supporting the development of targeted strategies to enhance surgical recovery and patient care in oncologic surgery settings.

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